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Bilyaminu Tijjani, Ph.D., Onipe Adabenege Yahaya, Ph.D.

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A bibliometric analysis of corporate ownership demographics and sustainability reporting quality in Nigeria

Bilyaminu Tijjani^{1*} and Onipe Adabenege Yahaya²

¹Department of Economics, * ²Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria
Email: bilyaminu@nda.edu.ng
Email: yoadabenege@nda.edu.ng
*Corresponding author

Abstract: This paper examines the influence of institutional and managerial ownership on sustainability reporting quality in Corporate Nigeria. Using a sample of 99 firms from 11 sectors as shown by the Nigerian Exchange between 2012 and 2021, we provide evidence that the presence of institutional ownership has positive and significant effect on sustainability reporting quality. However, we also provide evidence that the presence of managerial ownership has negative and significant effect on sustainability reporting quality. Furthermore, we find significant bivariate relationships between the control variables (leverage, age and firm size) and sustainability reporting quality. Though, while leverage is negative, age and firm size are positive. Our findings suggest that relevant legislations are beneficial and could be introduced in Nigeria where institutional and managerial investors are rare concepts in ownership structure discourse. These results form the basis to conduct further studies on sustainability reporting quality in Nigeria, since there is evidence that ownership structure has implications for sustainability reporting quality, especially in the institutional context of developing economies where sustainability reporting quality is still an emerging topic.

Keywords: age, firm size, institutional ownership, leverage, managerial ownership, Nigeria, ownership structure, sustainability reporting quality.

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Biographical notes: Dr Bilyaminu Tijjani holds two BSc degrees in Accounting and Economics, MBA from the Bayero University Kano, Nigeria, MSc Economics and a Ph.D. in Economics at the Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria. He is a Chartered Accountant. His research lies in internal audit, energy economics, financial accounting, fraud, and internal control.

Onipe Adabenege Yahaya is an Associate Professor of Accounting and Finance from the Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria. He holds a PhD in Accounting and Finance, MBA, MSc Accounting and Finance and BSc Accounting from the famous Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. His research interests revolve around accounting, finance, management, and corporate governance.

1 Introduction

As at the time of writing this paper, sustainability reporting is not mandatory in Nigeria. This might have explained the low level of sustainability reporting by listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX). This situation is similar to the adoption of international financial reporting standards, which were not until 2012, mandatory in Nigeria. Sustainability reporting is a non-financial reporting that enables corporations to express their improvement toward goals on a diversity of considerations, including environmental, social and governance, as well as risks and their effects, now or in the future. The inconsistency in the gravity of sustainability reporting in Nigeria is best illustrated in Figure 1.

Source: MachameRatios®

It is instructive to note that the discourse on non-financial reporting actually commences with corporate social responsibility reporting to environmental reporting and now sustainability reporting. Some scholars, such as Onyabe et al. (2016), Yahaya and Onyabe (2022) have even suggested the need to shift the conversations to integrated reporting, a situation in which both financial reports are combined with non-financial reports. Thus, integrated reporting is a situation, in which both financial reports and non-financial reports are published in the same annual reports and accounts for public consumption.

Furthermore, sustainability reporting has been scholarly linked with board governance (Shamil et al., 2014; Yahaya et al., 2022), financial performance (Umar et al., 2021; Uwuigbe et al., 2018), profitability (Yahaya & Alkasim, 2021) and firm value (Meini & Chotimah, 2022). Furthermore, it has been related with financial crisis (Garcia-Benau et al., 2013), enterprise risk management (Shad et al., 2019) and its drivers (Ikpore et al., 2022). There are few empirical works linking sustainability reporting quality in Nigeria.

There have been some empirical attempts at linking sustainability reporting with ownership structure in developed climes, and in the last two decades major empirical works have increased efforts. However, these efforts have yet to have any significant effect in developing countries, of which, Nigeria is one. This is the motivation of the study. Ownership structure is part of corporate governance mechanisms, designed to ensure that corporations are properly run. Other corporate governance mechanisms include regulators, lenders, boards of directors, CEOs, board committees, board diversity, and auditors.

Ownership structure is broadly divided into ten component parts: first largest shareholders, second largest shareholders, family ownership, managerial/board ownership, institutional ownership, core owners, government ownership, free float ownership, CEO ownership, and foreign ownership. Of interest in this paper are the effects of core owners (CO), institutional ownership (IO), and managerial or board ownership on sustainability reporting within corporate institutional context in Nigeria, an emerging economy. This is because several studies have used family and foreign ownership structures in their write ups. Also, since the implementation of privatization policy in Nigeria, there is no government ownership of shares among firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX).

According to Goldman Sachs Investment Bank (2022), Nigeria along with Bangladesh, Egypt, Indonesia, Iran, Mexico, Nigeria, Pakistan, Philippines, South Korea, Turkey, and Vietnam has a high potential of becoming the world's largest economies in the 21st century along with the BRICs. This view calls for several studies in order to ensure that the potentials are realized. This is because the World Bank in 1952 had ranked Nigeria as having potential ahead of Japan; but today, the story is different. While Japan is the world's third largest economy by gross domestic product, Nigeria is ranked as number thirty-three in the world economies ranking by the same World Bank (2022).

This article is an attempt to examine the effects of ownership structure on sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The different structures of ownership of firm's equity capital are such as core ownership (ownership concentration), institutional ownership, and managerial or board ownership. This study is one of the few that examines the relationship between ownership structure and reliability sustainability reporting in Nigeria. In addition, based on the existing literature, ownership structure is measured using three different ownership structures.

The remaining component parts of this paper is divided into four: literature review, methodology, results and discussion, and conclusions and recommendations. The part on literature consists of conceptual literature review, theoretical literature review and empirical literature review. The part of methodology discusses the research design, population and sample of this paper, model specification, variables definitions and measurements, sources and methods of data collection and analysis techniques and diagnostic tests.

2 Literature review and hypotheses development

2.1 Institutional ownership and sustainability reporting quality

Institutional ownership structure brings to bear a lot of corporate experience, expertise and power on firms willing to embrace sustainability reporting. Institutional ownership simply refers to ownership structure held by corporations in another corporations. It is the amount of a company's equity owned by mutual or pension funds, insurance companies, investment firms, private foundations, endowments or other large entities that manage funds on behalf of others.

In terms of empirical studies, Abd-Mutalib et al. (2015) examine if sustainability reporting exerts impact on the share ownership of 285 Malaysian firms for 2010 and 2011. The results reveal that sustainability reporting has a positive impact on institutional ownership. Also, Nulla (2016) explores the correlation between sustainability reporting and institutional ownership in US for 2012 to 2014. Findings suggest that sustainability reporting has a significant correlation with the institutional ownership. Furthermore, Novitaningrum and Amboningtyas (2017) analyze the influence of institutional ownership on sustainability reporting of 40 Manufacturing Sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) in the Year 2011-2016. The result of the research shows that institutional ownership has positive and significant influence on sustainability reporting.

Masud et al. (2018) draw 88 listed firms from Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan's sustainability reports during the years 2009–2016 from the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) database. Empirical results indicate that sustainability reporting has a positive association with institutional ownership. Furthermore, Aman and Jaafar (2020) investigate the influence of institutional ownership on corporate sustainability reporting of 771 listed companies from 2014 to 2016. Finding shows that institutional ownership influence corporate sustainability reporting.

Indy et al. (2021) examine the effect of institutional ownership on sustainability reporting of mining sector and the basic and chemical industry sectors listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange from 2015 to 2019. The results show that institutional ownership has no effect on sustainability reporting. Also, Delfy and Bimo (2021) analyze institutional ownership's direct effect on sustainability reporting of non-financial companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for 2016-2019. The results provide empirical evidence that institutional ownership has a positive effect on sustainability reporting. Furthermore, Alomran and Alshahli (2023) investigate the association between institutional ownership and sustainability reporting. The results find that institutional ownership is positively and significantly associated with sustainability reporting. Based on these findings, the second hypothesis is as follows:

H₁ Institutional ownership has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria.

2.2 Managerial ownership structure and sustainability reporting

In the same vein, managerial ownership, also known as board ownership is an important tool for motivating board members to work towards achieving greater height for the firm. The rationale is that board members would be encouraged when they are part of the owners of a firm. It is the percentage of shares held by the management who actively participate in corporate decisions. Novitaningrum and Amboningtyas (2017) analyze the influence of institutional ownership, managerial ownership on sustainability reporting of 40 Manufacturing Sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) in the Year 2011-2016. The result of the research shows that managerial ownership has positive effect not significant to sustainability reporting. Also, Masud et al. (2018) find director share ownership (managerial ownership) significantly relates with sustainability reporting.

Furthermore, Madona and Khafid (2020) analyze the effect of managerial ownership on sustainability report disclosures with firm size as a moderating variable of 41 mining sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2015-2017. The results show that managerial ownership does not affect the disclosure of sustainability report. In addition, managerial ownership moderated by firm size did not the affect the disclosure of sustainability reports. In the same vein, Indy et al. (2021) examine the effect of managerial ownership on sustainability reporting in Indonesia from 2015 to 2019.

The results show that managerial ownership has no effect on sustainability reporting. Based on these findings, the second hypothesis is as follows:

H₂ Managerial ownership has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria.

2.3 *Leverage, age and firm size and sustainability reporting*

Shamil et al. (2014) investigate the influence of board characteristics on sustainability reporting of listed companies in the Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE), Sri Lanka using a sample of 148 listed companies for 2012 annual reports. The study finds that sustainability reporting is influenced by firm size. Additionally, the study also reveals that younger firms adopt sustainability reporting. Also, Dienes et al. (2016) who earlier examine the drivers of sustainability reporting, find firm size as one of the drivers. However, in the study, leverage (capital structure) and firm age are not drivers of sustainability reporting.

Also, Bhatia and Tuli (2017) examine the relationship between sustainability reporting by companies and selected corporate specific attributes of 158 Indian companies selected from BSE 200. The analysis in this study reveals that companies with large size and older age have significant sustainability disclosure. However, company's leverage is negatively related with the extent of sustainability disclosure. Furthermore, Orazalin and Mahmood (2018) explore the extent and nature of sustainability reporting practices of the largest public oil and gas companies in Russia. It also investigates the impacts of possible underlying factors on the quality of sustainability information. The results reveal that firm age is one the main factors in the dissemination of sustainability information in the Russian context. In addition, Karaman et al. (2018) investigate empirically what affects Global Reporting Initiative (GRI)-based sustainability reporting in the aviation industry between 2006 and 2015. The results show that firm size and leverage are positively associated with sustainability reporting.

Karlina et al. (2019) examine the effects of company's size and leverage on disclosure of sustainability report of 20 companies during the observation period 2014-2016. The results of this study indicate that leverage affect the disclosure sustainability report. While size of the company, does not affect the disclosure sustainability report. Correa-Garcia et al. (2020) find firm age improves the quality of sustainability reporting. Also, Antara et al. (2020) examine the effect of company size and leverage on the area of sustainability reporting of 8 companies listed in the LQ45 index for the 2015-2018 period. Based on the results of the analysis it was found that company size has a positive and significant effect on the area of sustainability reporting. While leverage does not influence the sustainability reporting.

Furthermore, Sonia and Khafid (2020) obtain empirical evidence about the effects of leverage and company size to sustainability report disclosure of 465 non-financial companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2015-2017. The results of the analysis show that leverage and firm size have negative and significant effects on sustainability report disclosure. In addition, Ezejiofor and Emeneka (2022) examine the effect of leverage on sustainability reporting of 7 listed Oil and Gas firms in Nigeria for the years 2010 and 2020. Findings from the empirical analysis show that leverage has significant effect on sustainability reporting in Nigeria.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data collection method

This paper uses a correlational approach to examine the effects of ownership structures on sustainability. The model is based on a multiple regression analysis. The method of document mining is used for data collection from the annual reports and accounts of sampled firms. The data used in this study has been obtained from the companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange of 99 companies.

3.2 Sample selection procedure

99 firms are hand-picked from a population of 156 firms. 57 firms are excluded on the strength of failure to comply with the regulatory standards of the Nigerian Exchange (NGX, July 2023). The sectors are 11 (see Table 1).

Table 1

Listed firms in Nigerian Exchange

S/N	Sector	Number	Active	Non-active
1	Agriculture	5	3	2
2	Conglomerates	6	0	0
3	Construction/real estate	8	6	2
4	Consumer goods	21	12	9
5	Financial services	49	32	17
6	Healthcare	7	5	2
7	ICT	9	6	3
8	Industrial goods	13	11	2
9	Natural resources	4	2	2
10	Oil and gas	10	6	4
11	Services	23	16	7
Total		156	99	57

Source: <https://ngxgroup.com/exchange/trade/equities/listed-companies/>

Therefore, we believe that our sample constitutes the appropriate setting to test the proposed hypotheses because all the sectors in Nigeria are represented. Finally, 990 year-company observations are collected from 2012 to 2021.

3.3 Measurement of variables

The model is expressed in econometric terms as follows:

$$SR_{it} = a_0 + a_1CO_{it} + a_2IO_{it} + a_3MO_{it} + a_4SIZE_{it} + a_5AGE_{it} + a_6LEV_{it} + u_{it}$$

Whereas:

SR = Sustainability reporting, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to firm with annual reports with sustainability information and "0" for otherwise.

CO = Core owners (ownership concentration), measured as the shares ownership concentration of all the block shareholders with 5% and above shares ownership (%).

IO = Institutional ownership, measured as the shares ownership concentration of all the block institutional shareholders with 5% and above shares ownership (%).

MO = Managerial ownership, measured as directors' direct and indirect shares divided by the numbers of shares (%).

SIZE = Firm size, measured as natural log of total asset.

AGE = Firm age, measured as number of years a company is trading in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

LEV = Leverage, measured as total liabilities divided by total asset.

a_{1-6} = Beta coefficients.

i = Firm script ($i = 99$ firms).

t = Time script ($t = 10$ years).

4 Results, hypothesis testing and discussion

4.1 Descriptive analysis

The descriptive statistics are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SR	990	.512	.501	0	1
IO	990	27.919	23.624	0	89
MO	990	9.077	13.611	0	71.6
LEV	990	86.32	19.832	8.63	254.75
AGE	990	22.225	15.331	2	50
SIZE	990	8.992	.489	8.03	10.77

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

According to the results of Table 1, the average of *SR* is .512, which is almost half of the firms, meaning that only about half of the firms provide sustainability reports. Also, its standard deviation (.501) is almost equal to the mean, meaning that *SR* is highly volatile and variable; thus, validating the need to embark on further studies on it. Table 1 further indicates that the measures of *SR* are lowest (0) and maximum (1), which are dummy variables, suggesting that the model is binary. Furthermore, the average of *IO* is 27.919 percent, which is high enough in order to ensure good corporate governance. Also, its standard deviation (23.624) is a little less than the mean, meaning that *IO* is volatile and calls for managerial attention. Thus, suggesting the need to embark on further studies on it.

Table 1 further indicates that the measures of *IO* are lowest (0) percent and maximum (89) percent, implying that some firms do not have institutional investors. Also, the average of *MO* is 9.077 percent. Also, its standard deviation (13.611) is far greater than its mean, meaning that *MO* is highly volatile and requires managerial attention. Thus, suggesting the need to embark on further studies on it. Table 1 further indicates that the measures of *MO* are lowest (0) percent and maximum (71.6) percent, implying that some firms do not allocate shares to top management.

In terms of the control variables, the average of *LEV* is 89.32 percent, which is high and calls management strategies to reduce the level of leverage. Also, its standard deviation is 19.832 percent, meaning that *LEV* is not volatile but calls for measures to reduce it. Thus, suggesting the need to embark on further studies on it. Table 1 further indicates that the measures of *MO* are lowest (8.63) percent and maximum (254.75) percent, implying that some firms have extremely high gearing rate. In the same vein, the average *AGE* of the firms is about 22 years with a standard deviation of 15 years, which is lower than the mean, suggesting that there is source of concern. Table 1 further indicates that the measures of *AGE* are lowest (2 years) and maximum (50) years. Finally, the average of *SIZE* is 8.992 point. Also, its standard deviation is .489 point, meaning that *SIZE* is not volatile.

The results of correlation analysis are reported in Table 2.

Table 2

Correlation matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) SR	1.000 (0.014)					
(2) IO	0.213* (0.007)	1.000				
(3) MO	-0.185* (0.019)	0.130 (0.101)	1.000			
(4) LEV	-0.157* (0.047)	0.085 (0.286)	0.332* (0.000)	1.000		
(5) AGE	0.185* (0.019)	-0.005 (0.954)	-0.165* (0.037)	0.112 (0.157)	1.000	
(6) SIZE	0.371* (0.000)	-0.182* (0.021)	-0.253* (0.001)	-0.294* (0.000)	0.208* (0.008)	1.000

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

According to the results of Table 2, the nexus between *IO* and *SR* is positive and significant at 1 percent. In contrast, the nexus between *MO* and *SR* is negative but significant at 5 percent. In the same vein, the nexus between *LEV* and *SR* is negative and significant at 5 percent. However, the nexus between *AGE* and *SR* is positive and significant at 5 percent. Furthermore, the nexus between *SIZE* and *SR* is positive and significant at 1 percent. Table 3 reports the results of variance inflation factor analysis.

Table 3

Variance inflation factors (VIF)

	VIF	1/VIF
LEV	1.253	.798
SIZE	1.218	.821
MO	1.207	.828
AGE	1.122	.892
IO	1.045	.957
Mean VIF	1.169	.

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

According to the results of Table 3, there is no multicollinearity among the variables. For example, even the mean VIF is 1.169. Also, the VIF of *LEV* is 1.253. Similarly, the VIF of *SIZE* is 1.218. Furthermore, the VIF of *MO* is 1.207, the VIF of *AGE* is 1.122, and the VIF of *IO* is 1.045. Table 4 reports the results of both normality of residuals test and heteroskedasticity of residuals test.

Table 4

Cameron & Trivedi's decomposition of IM-test

Source	chi2	df	p
Heteroskedasticity	47.190	20	0.001
Skewness	29.770	5	0.000
Kurtosis	24.180	1	0.000
Total	101.140	26	0.000

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

According to the results of Table 4, the p-value of heteroskedasticity is lower than .05, which is the threshold used in this paper. Furthermore, a normal distribution would have a Skewness of 0 and Kurtosis of 3. However, all of the variables have Skewness of 29.77 and Kurtosis of 24.18, indicating that the variables are not normally distributed. This is true because there is no way SR, measured by dummy variable (0, 1) would be normally distributed. Therefore, there is need to robust the model regression results by using robust standard errors instead of the ordinary standard errors. Figures 2-6 report evidence that the variables are not linear.

Figure 2 Fitted values and IO
Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Figure 3 Fitted values and MO
Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Figure 4 Fitted values and LEV
Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Figure 5 Fitted values and AGE
Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Figure 6 Fitted values and AGE

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

According to the results of Figures 2-6, the variables are not linear. Therefore, the model is non-linear. Furthermore, the results of model specification error tests are reported in Tables 5 and 6.

Table 5

Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of SR

Ho: model has no omitted variables

F(3, 151) = 2.72

Prob > F = 0.065

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

According to the results of Table 5, the p-value of omitted variable test is not significant, that is, it is higher than 0.05, suggesting that there is no problem of model specification error. Similarly, the results of Table 6 test the same model specification test.

Table 6

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 990	
			F(2, 987)	= 27.59	
Model	10.3965725	2	5.19828623	Prob > F	= 0.0000
Residual	29.5784275	157	.188397628	R-squared	= 0.801
				Adj R-squared	= 0.80
Total	39.975	159	.251415094	Root MSE	= .43405
SR	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf. Interval]
_hat	1.775322	.4325196	4.10	0.000	.9210135 2.62963
_hatsq	-.7527593	.3975868	-1.89	0.060	-1.538069 .0325498
_cons	-.1538995	.1134685	-1.36	0.177	-.3780212 .0702223

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

According to the results of Table 6, the p-value of linktest (.06) is not significant, that is, it is higher than 0.05, suggesting that there is no problem of model specification error in the model. Furthermore, the results of panel effects test are reported in Table 7.

Table 7

Breusch and Pagan Heteroskedasticity Test for random effects

$$SR_{iYEAR,t} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 YEAR_{i,t} + e_{iYEAR,t}$$

Estimated results:

	var	sd = sqrt(var)
SR	2514151	5014131
e	2002909	4475387
r	0	0

Test: Var(u) = 0

chi2(0) = 0.00
 Prob > chi2 = 1.0000

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

According to the results of Table 7, the p-value of χ^2 is 1, which is higher than 0.05 that is, there are no panel effects in the data set. Thus, there is no need for Hausman specification test, the Ordinary Least Squares regression is enough. The results of binary regression analysis are reported in Table 8.

Table 8

Logistic regression

SR	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
IO	1.035	.012	2.93	.003	1.011	1.059	***
MO	.985	.014	-2.06	.029	1.957	1.013	**
LEV	.968	.022	-2.39	.016	1.925	1.013	**
AGE	1.025	.016	2.57	.012	1.994	1.057	**
SIZE	6.907	2.898	4.61	.000	3.035	15.718	***
Constant	0	0	-3.74	.000	0	.001	***
Mean dependent var		0.512	SD dependent var			0.501	
Pseudo r-squared		0.80	Number of obs			990	
Chi-square		29.943	Prob > chi ²			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		187.679	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			206.130	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

According to the results of Table 8, the Prob > Chi² of the model is .000, which is significant. This shows that the model is fit and can be used to explain the effects of ownership structure on sustainability reporting quality. The R² of the model is 80 percent, which is considerably high, suggesting that 80 percent of the variations in sustainability reporting quality is explained by the model. In terms of the specifics, IO shows both positive and significant effect on sustainability reporting quality. However, MO shows both negative and significant effect on sustainability reporting quality. In terms of the control variables, leverage shows both negative and significant effect on sustainability reporting quality. However, age and size show positive and significant effects on sustainability reporting quality.

In view of these results, Hypothesis 1 is hereby rejected since it is significant, that is, its p-value is less than .05. Furthermore, the results are in line with the works of several scholars such as Abd-Mutalib et al. (2015), Nulla (2016), Novitaningrum and Amboningtyas (2017), Masud et al. (2018), Aman and Jaafar (2020), Delfy and Bimo (2021), Alomran and Alsahali (2023). Furthermore, Hypothesis 2 is hereby rejected since it is significant, that is, its p-value is less than .05. Furthermore, the results are in line with the work of Masud et al. (2018). In contrast, the result is not in agreement with the works of Madona and Khafid (2020), Indy et al. (2021).

In terms of control variables, the result on firm size is in line with the works of Antara et al. (2020), Shamil et al. (2014), Dienes et al. (2016) and Karaman et al. (2018), Bhatia and Tuki (2017) and Sonia and Khafid (2020). The result is in contrast with the work of Karlina et al. (2020). On firm age, the results are in line with the works of Bhatia and Tuli (2017), Orazalin and Mahmood (2018), and Correa-Garcia et al. (2020). On leverage, the result is in line with the works of Karaman et al. (2018), Karlina et al. (2020), Sonia and Khafid (2020), and Ezejiofor and Emeneka (2022). However, the result is not in line with the work of Anatara et al. (2020).

5 Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper examines the effects of ownership structure on sustainability reporting quality in Nigeria. Two hypotheses have been proposed to answer this question. Our findings confirm the first hypothesis, according to which the degree of institutional ownership is positively related to sustainability reporting quality. This finding is consistent with several scholars as indicated in the discussion section, which conclude that institutional ownership has a positive effect on sustainability reporting quality. For the second hypothesis (managerial ownership), the result shows that the degree of managerial ownership is negatively related to sustainability reporting quality.

This finding is consistent with several scholars as indicated in the discussion section, which conclude that managerial ownership has a negative effect on sustainability reporting quality. The results in this study are subject to some limitations in measuring ownership structure. In econometrics literature, the dummy measure of sustainability reporting quality calls for the use of binary logistic regression model.

We have considered the large statistical sample of 990 year-company to mitigate the potential problems arising from the mean comparison test to the normal distribution of data and outliers. While this increases our evidence's credibility, we cannot completely rule out alternative explanations due to the inherent limitations of the study. However, these limitations provide opportunities for future research. Our results also suggest avenues for further research to investigate the trade-off between ownership structure and sustainability reporting quality for firms listed in Nigeria.

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